

*This is the version of the article before peer review or editing, as submitted by an author to the Journal of Radiological Protection. IOP Publishing Ltd is not responsible for any errors or omissions in this version of the manuscript or any version derived from it. The Version of Record is available online at **DOI** [10.1088/1361-6498/ad53d5](https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6498/ad53d5)*

Object and person tracking systems for occupational dosimetry in nuclear medicine

Daniel Santiago Rondón^{1,2}, Pasquale Lombardo², Mahmoud Abdelrahman², Lara Struelens², Filip Vanhavere^{1,2}, Niki Bergans¹

¹ KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

² SCKCEN, Mol, Belgium

E-mail: daniel.santiago.rondon@sckcen.be, niki.bergans@kuleuven.be

August 2023

Abstract.

Nuclear Medicine (NM) professionals are potentially exposed to high doses of ionizing radiation, particularly in the skin of the hands. Ring dosimeters are used by the workers to ensure extremity doses are kept below the legal limits. However, ring dosimeters are often susceptible to large uncertainties, so it is difficult to ensure a correct measurement using the traditional occupational monitoring methods. An alternative solution is to calculate the absorbed dose by using Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. This method could reduce the uncertainty in dose calculation if the exact positions of the worker and the radiation source are represented in these simulations. In this study we present a set of computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms that allow us to track the exact position of unshielded syringes and the hands of NM workers. We showcase a possible hardware configuration to acquire the necessary input data for the algorithms. And finally, we assess the tracking confidence of our software. The tracking accuracy achieved for the syringe detection was 57% and for the hand detection 98%.

1. Introduction

Medical staff working in nuclear medicine (NM) departments are potentially exposed to high doses of ionizing radiation, especially in the skin of the hands during the preparation and injection of radiopharmaceuticals [1, 2, 3]. The radiation dose received by NM staff is monitored by using personal dosimeters. Typically, $H_p(10)$ dosimeters are used for assessing whole body doses, while $H_p(0.07)$ ring or wrist dosimeters are used for estimating doses to the skin of the hands [2, 4]. Dosimeters are read out monthly, to ensure the doses received are below the recommended limits [5]. Going above those limits can cause detrimental effects on organs and tissues, such as inducing the development of cancer, or causing deterministic skin effects [6].

Previous studies have shown that there is a real risk of exceeding legal doses in the skin of the hands for NM staff [2]. The value and location of the highest absorbed dose is affected by the position of the worker's hands and fingers with respect to the radiation source [7, 8], they change according to individual worker techniques, and even from one day to another [9]. This variability makes it difficult to assess the maximum dose somewhere on the hands using a single dosimeter, as there is no "correct" position to wear it. NM workers usually wear a single ring dosimeter; using more than one might hamper the manipulation of radioactive sources, increasing the manipulation time or the contamination risk. Moreover, ring dosimeters are mostly worn in the proximal phalanx, but the highest dose is often received on the fingertips [1]. The response of dosimeters is also affected by energy and angular sensitivity [10], which further increases the uncertainty in dose measurements. The combination of these factors can lead to incorrect dose assessments and emphasizes the importance of developing an alternative technique for extremity dosimetry that can overcome the aforementioned problems.

1.1. Monte Carlo simulations for occupational dose calculation

An alternative approach to occupational dose estimation in NM is the use of Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. By using simulations, it is possible to score the dose received across different sections of the hands and to identify the section that receives the maximum dose. However, to obtain accurate results from MC simulations, the exact hand posture of NM workers should be represented, as well as the distance from the hands to the radiation source. This makes it impossible to represent the injection or preparation of radiopharmaceuticals in a single simulation, as the hands and the radiation source are in constant movement. Instead, several simulations can be created to represent all the adopted positions of the hands and the source, then integrate the dose calculated over all the simulations to obtain a final dose approximation per preparation, dispensing or administration procedure.

This multi-simulation approach was first explored during the PODIUM research project, where an online dosimetry application was implemented and validated for 2 different scenarios: neutron workplaces and interventional radiology [11, 12]. The purpose of this application was to perform personal dosimetry in real-time using multiple

MC simulations. Each simulation represents the posture and position of the workers with respect to the radiation source during a small time window. The posture and position are identified in real-time using computer vision algorithms and recreated in the simulations using last generation computational phantoms [13]. An advantage of this application is that it allows to visualize near real-time dose assessments, which is useful as an ALARA tool, gets rid of organizational issues related to the distribution and wearing of physical dosimeters, and it is not limited by the inherent uncertainties from physical dosimeters.

The PODIUM approach could be extended to calculate occupational doses for NM staff; however, it needs to be adapted to specific requirements that are not considered in the original applications. The PODIUM application can track the whole body of workers, but it does not account for the exact position of the hands and fingers, nor the used computational phantom can represent detailed hand postures. As mentioned earlier, representing the exact hand posture of the workers is necessary for the NM application, since the posture can influence the value and location of the maximum skin dose. The type of radiation source and radiation shielding also varies in different NM laboratories, where the source is typically the radiopharmaceuticals inside a syringe or vial, and the radiation shielding used depends on the performed operation. Shielding of radiopharmaceuticals in vials can be done by using lead vial containers while for administration the use of syringe shields is recommended. Manual dispensing is sometimes done without syringe shielding because the unshielded syringe needs to be placed in a radionuclide activity calibrator to measure the amount of radioactivity at a defined time [14].

In this study, we develop a method to automatically identify the position of unshielded syringes and the hand posture of NM workers using AI and computer vision algorithms. The developed method works also in real-time, so the simulation input files can be created on the fly. As the input for the tracking algorithms is a streamed video of the source manipulation, we also configured a special hardware setup, able to stream and record the video. This setup is designed to work in a real environment such as a NM or radiopharmacy departments, therefore the portable setup can be attached to walls or mounted inside a laminar airflow cabinet. This paper, and the algorithms developed, are the first step towards an automatic, computational dosimetry system for NM, that will require minimum effort to setup, while still providing the best dose calculations available for NM staff. The expected workflow of the upcoming system is shown in Figure 1.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Monitoring system

The methods developed for 3D tracking of hands and syringes require a video input of the source manipulation. We configured a hardware setup to obtain such videos

Figure 1: Dosimetry system workflow.

and stream them in real-time to a computing cluster, that will create and run the simulations. The setup consists of a microcomputer and a video camera, and it is focused on high portability and compactness which allows us to place the monitoring system in laboratories or hospital rooms without interfering with the work of NM professionals. The camera can be mounted on a suction cup and attached to walls or difficult to reach surfaces. It can be wiped with a disinfectant solution and placed inside a laminar airflow cabinet to monitor the preparation of radiopharmaceuticals (Figure2).

The camera used is an Intel RealSense LiDAR L515 [15], it is a depth camera of size 61 mm x 26 mm x 61 mm, specially designed for measuring the distance to different points within its field of view (FOV). It creates a point cloud representation, that can be queried to get the depth of the pixels (distance to the camera) in a photography. The point cloud can be used to map pixels into real world coordinates using the camera's FOV and the pixel's depth. It's connected to the micro-computer using a USB-C to USB-A cable.

The micro-computer used is an NVIDIA Jetson Nano [16] (Figure3), specifically designed for artificial intelligence and edge computing applications. The computer's task is to control the video stream from the camera and send the raw information to a computer cluster that will run the tracking algorithms, create the MC input files, and run the MC simulations. The video can be streamed using either an Ethernet connection or wireless connection.

2.2. Hand Detection

To track the hands of NM personnel, two different libraries for person detection and tracking were investigated: OpenPose [17] and MediaPipe [18]. The algorithms in these libraries allow us to recognize hands and people using a video input. The output is a

Figure 2: Intel RealSense LiDAR L515 inside a laminar airflow cabinet.

Figure 3: NVIDIA Jetson Nano.

frame-by-frame set of connected points representing the position of several finger and hand joints. The results of applying the hand detection algorithms to a single picture are shown in Figure 4.

During our first tests in a NM department, the detection algorithms were unable to identify the hands of the workers that were using disposable gloves, which is mandatory for handling unsealed sources of radiation. These algorithms were trained to recognize naked hands, but disposable gloves, usually purple or blue, have a very different color spectrum compared to skin. So, an algorithm was developed to adjust the color of every frame in the streamed video. The algorithm changes the color code of any pixel of the

gloves' color, for a skin-like color, keeping the color intensity and brightness of the pixel.

A comparison of the capabilities of both libraries was carried out, testing the performance according to speed, accuracy, and camera distance to achieve an accurate detection (Figure 4). The experiments were performed using 2 different computers to test a low-end and a high-end hardware configuration. Since OpenPose has several detection models which can be selected from (balancing performance and computational resources), the comparisons were made using the standard configurations for CPU and GPU implementations of OpenPose. For Mediapipe, the standard detection and tracking confidence values were used.

To compare the speed of the tracking algorithms, we measure the number of frames per second (FPS) they can process. This speed is also tightly related to the computational resources needed to execute the algorithms. To measure the range of accurate detection, we recorded a person walking towards the camera and away from the camera and identified the minimum and maximum range of detection. To measure the accuracy, we applied the algorithms to prerecorded videos representing the dispensing of 10 syringes of Tc-99m for sentinel procedures. The videos were recorded using the RealSense camera inside the laminar airflow cabinet.

Figure 4: Output from the hand detection methods. OpenPose on the left side and MediaPipe on the right side.

2.3. Source detection

In this study, as a first step, we focus on the situations where the highest dose rates are reached, identifying in the video unshielded syringes. To detect the syringe, we apply two different algorithms. The first algorithm creates an initial approximation, identifying the syringe within a bounding box. The second algorithm works on top of the initial approximation to refine the assessed location of the syringe and calculate its orientation.

2.3.1. Bounding box approximation: As a first attempt to approximate the syringe's position we trained a Neural Network for object detection. These networks are trained using a data set of annotated images. The annotations identify the targeted object(s)

using a label and a bounding box [19, 20]. Once trained, the network can detect the position of the object(s) in a picture and assign a likelihood of correctness to the detected position. Our neural network was trained using TensorFlow Object Detection API [21]. The used data set included more than 10K images, obtained in a variety of environments including realistic backgrounds. Most of the pictures were obtained in the radiopharmacy laboratory of the nuclear medicine department of UZ Leuven in Belgium. Some pictures were taken in different scenarios to increase the heterogeneity in background and lighting conditions. The base topology of the network was taken from the SSD MobileNet v2 320x320 network in the TensorFlow Object Detection Zoo [22], previously trained with the COCO 2017 dataset [23].

All the pictures in the data set included at least a hand holding an unshielded syringe, always wearing gloves but using different colors to increase the variability in the training set. To speed up the creation of the data set, instead of taking individual pictures, we took videos of syringe manipulations from different angles. The videos were divided into several frames, blurry ones were filtered out, using only clear images. Seventy percent of all the data was used for the training and thirty percent for validation. Classic strategies of data augmentation were implemented in the training phase, such as image mirroring and random cropping.

Another alternative to approximate the syringe's position is to identify the position of the dominant hand and create a bounding box around it. Based on the output from the hands tracking, it is possible to differentiate the left and the right hand. If the dominant hand is known in advance, we can create a bounding box around it that should contain the syringe most of the time. Assuming the syringe is held in the dominant hand, the method accuracy relies mostly on the hand tracking. To completely contain the syringe within, the bounding box should be centered in the hand's center and should be at least twice the size of the hand in every axis.

Regardless of the chosen alternative, this first estimation provides a bounding box containing the syringe within its limits. The bounding box does not specify the orientation of the syringe and it might not be as tight as necessary to identify the extremes. While this approximation provides a general idea of the syringe position, a more precise location is needed to create a digital twin. The main purpose of this first approximation is to reduce the search space of the syringe detection algorithm. This algorithm works on top of the bounding box, refining the assessed location of the syringe by identifying its exact position and orientation within the bounding box.

2.3.2. Syringe detection: To identify the syringe within the bounding box, we use the color and depth information from each picture. We apply two different filters, a color filter to identify the pixels of "syringe color", and a distance filter to identify the pixels at the "right distance". In this study we focused on identifying the transparent-white color of an unshielded syringe, so the color filter removes the pixels from the initial approximation that have a different color. This removes already a great part of the pixels, but in many cases, the laboratory coat or other objects in the background share

the same color of the syringe, so it is not enough to isolate the syringe in the picture. The second filter removes the pixels that are considered too far from the hand center. We calculate an approximation of the hand’s center by averaging the 3D positions of all the identified joints of the hand. Any point that is further than 10 centimeters from the center is not considered part of the syringe and gets eliminated as well. After applying both filters, the remaining pixels are likely to be part of the syringe as they have the correct color and the correct distance from the camera and the center of the hand. Running a simple linear regression on the 3D position of the remaining pixels provides us with a function that represents the exact orientation of the syringe.

To measure the accuracy of the source detection we applied the algorithms to prerecorded videos corresponding to the dispensing of 10 syringes of Tc-99m for sentinel procedures. The videos were recorded using the RealSense camera inside a laminar airflow cabinet. We calculated the accuracy of the syringe detection using each of the proposed methods for bounding box detection and followed by the color and distance filters to obtain the syringe orientation. It is important to note that the accuracy of the syringe detection will heavily depend on the accuracy of the assessed bounding box, since the algorithms are applied in sequence.

3. Results

3.1. Hands Detection

The speed of the algorithms was tested on two different computers, the Jetson Nano used for data acquisition, and a workstation with higher computing capabilities (Table 1). On the workstation, the average speed achieved by OpenPose hands tracking was 8 FPS using the GPU version and 0.1 FPS using the CPU version. In contrast, the average speed achieved by MediaPipe in the same computer was 27 FPS. With the Jetson Nano it was impossible to run OpenPose hand tracking using either GPU or CPU versions due to memory limitations; however, MediaPipe hands tracking ran at 15 FPS.

Computer	Jetson Nano	Workstation
CPU	Quad-core ARM Cortex-A57 1.43 GHz	Intel(R) Xeon(R) W-1290P 3.70GHz
GPU	NVIDIA Maxwell 128 CUDA cores	NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000
RAM	4GB DDR4	64GB DDR4
Storage	MicroSD card	SSD drive

Table 1: Computer comparison.

Both detection methods benefited from changing the color of the gloves to a skin-like color. The method used to make the color change has to pass by every pixel of every frame in the video, but our efficient implementation does not slow down the hand

tracking speed by more than a frame per second. The results of this algorithm can be appreciated in figure 5.

Figure 5: Demonstration of the color change algorithm.

Based on our experiments, the maximum distance from the camera for hand detection using MediaPipe is 4 meters, while using OpenPose it is 8 meters. However, MediaPipe has a feature that allows the tracking of previously detected hands, increasing the recognition distance to 6 meters. For minimum range, MediaPipe can recognize hands as close as the FOV allows, which is 20 cm using the Intel RealSense LiDAR L515 camera. In contrast, OpenPose requires to recognize the whole body in order to recognize its hands, which can increase the minimum distance to more than 2 meters away. This is impractical in most scenarios, as we expect to place the camera inside a laminar airflow cabinet. However, it is possible for OpenPose to partially identify the body at close range, but the accuracy of hands detection suffers from the partial detection. Our accuracy test showed better results for MediaPipe than OpenPose at such close range, the former achieved an almost perfect 98% accuracy, while the latter achieved 30% accuracy.

Table 2: OpenPose vs MediaPipe comparison for hands detection.

Computer	OpenPose	MediaPipe
Jetson Nano Speed (GPU/CPU)	-/- FPS	15 FPS
Workstation Speed (GPU/CPU)	8/0.1 FPS	27 FPS
Tracking Accuracy	30%	98 %
Maximum Range	8 m	4 to 6 m
Minimum Range	Requires body detection	0.2 m (Based on the camera FOV)

3.2. Source detection

The accuracy of the syringe detection is related to the accuracy of the initial bounding box estimation because they work in a sequence. We calculated the overall accuracy of the syringe detection using both of the proposed alternatives for bounding box estimation and also compared the accuracy of the bounding box approaches itself. The best results for the overall syringe detection use the dominant hand approximation as a base, identifying the syringe's position and orientation 57% of the time. The dominant hand approximation itself was able to identify a correct bounding box around the syringe 65% of the time. In contrast, the overall syringe detection algorithm using the neural network as a base, was only able to recognize the syringe 5% of the time, which comes from the fact that the neural network alone recognized a proper bounding box 10% of the time. The detection accuracy was thus mainly affected by the bounding box approximation, with the overall syringe detection identifying the syringe position and orientation 88% (dominant hand) and 50% (neural network) of the frames where the bounding box was correct.

Figure 6: (a) Original image. (b) Results of applying the distance filter on top of the bounding box enclosing the syringe. (c) Results of applying the color filter after the distance filter. (d) Final assessment of the position and orientation of the syringe, obtained from applying a linear regression to the resulting pixels.

4. Discussion

4.1. Hands detection

The algorithm to change the color of gloves to a skin-like color increases the chances of recognizing the hands of workers but requires knowing in advance the color of the gloves used. This should not be a major problem as it can be solved by selecting from predefined colors in the software. However, using white gloves can affect the syringe

detection as the color of the syringe would be very similar to the gloves' color. It is very likely that hand points would be considered as syringe points and hence the assessed position would not be correct.

The performance of MediaPipe was better than OpenPose for almost every aspect measured, requiring a lower computational power to achieve a higher actualization rate. On top of that, OpenPose requires identifying the body posture of the worker to recognize the hands, this reduces the capabilities of our system for many scenarios where the hands of the worker are inside a laminar airflow cabinet. The main advantage of OpenPose over MediaPipe in this application is the possibility of recognizing the hands at long distance, but we do not see it as a limitation, since for most practical situations the camera can be placed at 50 cm to 3 meters distance from the hands.

4.2. Source detection

The Neural Network for syringe detection didn't perform as good as expected. The model was trained with data that had very little in common with the data used for the validation, resulting in poor performance. We attribute it to a poor generalization capability, induced by the lack of heterogeneity of the used data set. However, this is an issue that can be solved by increasing the amount of backgrounds and light conditions of the images used for the training. Another solution is to train the model with the same background and light conditions it will be used in practice, i.e. the same place. That will reduce the amount of data necessary for the training but will make the model usable only under those specific conditions.

On the other hand, the dominant hand approximation performed well in a variety of scenarios, mainly due to the high accuracy of the hand tracking algorithm and the fact that the syringe is usually held in the dominant hand. Also, the usage of color and distance filters might help to reduce the false negative situations, where an empty hand is considered as a possible hand holding a syringe. While retraining the neural network for syringe detection might increase the accuracy of the initial approximation, it requires a lot of work, and using the dominant hand is still a valid alternative that can perform sufficiently well.

From a computer vision point of view, the source detection as a whole can still be improved. However, from a dosimetry point of view the results achieved in this paper might be already enough to create accurate MC simulations. Some smart decision making can be done to represent the moments for which we do not have tracking information, such as creating the 3D model in the last known position of the syringe or to estimate the unknown positions based on previous and subsequent positions. The impact of the tracking accuracy on the dose calculation needs to be measured after applying such techniques as they can impact positively the overall accuracy of the MC simulations.

The object detection methods we presented can be extended to identify different objects such as vials or radiation shields, as a similar procedure can be applied for the

recognition of such objects. This is in fact one of the objectives of our current research to create a Monte Carlo simulation framework for dosimetry in NM. In the future we will further explore the possibilities of object detection combined with automatic segmentation to identify the most common laboratory objects that might influence the dose calculation.

5. Conclusions

The methodology presented in this paper can track the positions of syringes and hands on a video recording with good accuracy. The tracking algorithms will facilitate the creation of digital twins for hands and syringes in the exact positions adopted by the NM workers. The digital twins can be used for the creation of Monte Carlo simulations, which, supported by the accuracy and fast-tracking capabilities of the models, will decrease the uncertainty in extremity dose calculations for Nuclear Medicine professionals. Also, a Monte Carlo simulation framework able to integrate these tracking methodologies will be useful in the identification of bad practices where high doses to hands and fingers are the result from proximity to or direct contact with small and strong radiation sources. With this methodology dose maps of the hands based on the digital twin and MC simulation can be displayed in colour scale to facilitate hotspot detection. NM staff can use this to reflect on their work practices and think about the different ways of reducing their extremity dose received (exposure time, shielding objects, distance tools). Therefore this methodology can also serve as training and ALARA tool for NM practitioners to optimize the occupational dose.

Acknowledgments

Some of the authors have received funding for this project from Euratom's research and innovation programme 2019-20 under grant agreement no. 945196 (SINFONIA Project)

References

- [1] Robert Kollaard, Alessandra Zorz, Jérémie Dabin, Peter Covens, Jennie Cooke, Melissa Crabbé, Lidia Cunha, Anita Dowling, Mercè Ginjaume, and Leanne McNamara. Review of extremity dosimetry in nuclear medicine. *Journal of Radiological Protection*, 41(4):R60, 2021.
- [2] Filip Vanhavere, E Carinou, L Donadille, M Ginjaume, J Jankowski, A Rimpler, and M Sans Merce. An overview on extremity dosimetry in medical applications. *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 129(1-3):350–355, 2008.
- [3] M Wrzesień, J Olszewski, and J Jankowski. Hand exposure to ionising radiation of nuclear medicine workers. *Radiation protection dosimetry*, 130(3):325–330, 2008.
- [4] A. Carnicer, M. Sans-Merce, S. Baechler, I. Barth, L. Donadille, P. Ferrari, M. Fulop, M. Ginjaume, G. Gualdrini, S. Krim, M. Mariotti, X. Ortega, A. Rimpler, N. Ruiz, and F. Vanhavere. Hand exposure in diagnostic nuclear medicine with 18f- and 99mtc-labelled radiopharmaceuticals - results of the oramed project. *Radiation Measurements*, 46(11):1277–1282, 2011. International Workshop on Optimization of Radiation Protection of Medical Staff, ORAMED 2011.

- [5] Monty W. Charles. ICRP Publication 103: Recommendations of the ICRP†. *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*, 129(4):500–507, 05 2008.
- [6] United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation et al. *Sources and Effects of Ionizing Radiation, United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR) 1993 Report: Report to the General Assembly, with Scientific Annexes*. United Nations, 1993.
- [7] Fabien Salesses, Paul Perez, Aline E Maillard, Julie Blanchard, Sabine Mallard, and Laurence Bordenave. Effect of dosimeter’s position on occupational radiation extremity dose measurement for nuclear medicine workers during 18f-fdg preparation for pet/ct. *EJNMMI physics*, 3(1):1–12, 2016.
- [8] P Ferrari, M Sans-Merce, A Carnicer, L Donadille, M Fulop, M Ginjaume, G Gualdrini, F Mariotti, and N Ruiz. Main results of the monte carlo studies carried out for nuclear medicine practices within the oramed project. *Radiation measurements*, 46(11):1287–1290, 2011.
- [9] A.L.S.L. Kubo and C.L.P. Mauricio. Tld occupational dose distribution study in nuclear medicine. *Radiation Measurements*, 71:442–446, 2014. Proceedings of the 17th Solid State Dosimetry Conference (SSD17).
- [10] H. Stadtmann, A. McWhan, M. Figel, T.W.M. Grimbergen, A.M. Romero, and Ch. Gärtner. Eurados intercomparisons for individual monitoring services: Results of the 2015 extremity dosimeter intercomparison for photon and beta radiations. *Radiation Measurements*, 106:285–289, 2017. Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Solid State Dosimetry (SSD18), Munich, Germany, 3 – 8 July 2016.
- [11] Mahmoud Abdelrahman, Pasquale Lombardo, Filip Vanhavere, Alain Seret, Christophe Phillips, and Peter Covens. First steps towards online personal dosimetry using computational methods in interventional radiology: Operator’s position tracking and simulation input generation. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 171:108702, 2020.
- [12] Olivier Van Hoey, Mahmoud Abdelrahman, Filip Vanhavere, Pasquale Lombardo, JS Eakins, LG Hager, JTM Jansen, and RJ Tanner. Computational personal dosimetry at a realistic neutron workplace field. *Radiation Measurements*, 159:106867, 2022.
- [13] Pasquale A Lombardo, Filip Vanhavere, Anne L Lebacq, Lara Struelens, and Ria Bogaerts. Development and validation of the realistic anthropomorphic flexible (raf) phantom. *Health physics*, 114(5):486–499, 2018.
- [14] Nic Gillings, Olaug Hjelstuen, Jim Ballinger, Martin Behe, Clemens Decristoforo, Philip Elsinga, Valentina Ferrari, Petra Kolenc Peitl, Jacek Kozirowski, Peter Laverman, Thomas L. Mindt, Oliver Neels, Meltem Ocak, Marianne Patt, and Sergio Todde. Guideline on current good radiopharmacy practice (cgrpp) for the small-scale preparation of radiopharmaceuticals. *EJNMMI Radiopharmacy and Chemistry*, 6(1), February 2021.
- [15] Intel realsense lidar camera l515 datasheet. <https://dev.intelrealsense.com/docs/lidar-camera-1515-datasheet>.
- [16] Nvidia jetson nano data sheet. <https://developer.nvidia.com/downloads/embedded/dlc/jetson-nano-system-module-datasheet>.
- [17] Zhe Cao, Gines Hidalgo, Tomas Simon, Shih-En Wei, and Yaser Sheikh. Openpose: Realtime multi-person 2d pose estimation using part affinity fields, 2019.
- [18] Fan Zhang, Valentin Bazarevsky, Andrey Vakunov, Andrei Tkachenka, George Sung, Chuo-Ling Chang, and Matthias Grundmann. Mediapipe hands: On-device real-time hand tracking, 2020.
- [19] Christian Szegedy, Alexander Toshev, and Dumitru Erhan. Deep neural networks for object detection. In C.J. Burges, L. Bottou, M. Welling, Z. Ghahramani, and K.Q. Weinberger, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 26. Curran Associates, Inc., 2013.
- [20] Wei Liu, Dragomir Anguelov, Dumitru Erhan, Christian Szegedy, Scott Reed, Cheng-Yang Fu, and Alexander C Berg. Ssd: Single shot multibox detector. In *Computer Vision–ECCV 2016: 14th European Conference, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, October 11–14, 2016, Proceedings, Part I 14*, pages 21–37. Springer, 2016.

- [21] Tensorflow object detection api. https://github.com/tensorflow/models/blob/master/research/object_detection/g3doc/tf2.md.
- [22] Tensorflow 2 object detection zoo. https://github.com/tensorflow/models/blob/master/research/object_detection/g3doc/tf2_detection_zoo.md.
- [23] Tsung-Yi Lin, Michael Maire, Serge Belongie, James Hays, Pietro Perona, Deva Ramanan, Piotr Dollár, and C Lawrence Zitnick. Microsoft coco: Common objects in context. In *European conference on computer vision*, pages 740–755. Springer, 2014.